

ASPECTS OF PROFESSIONAL AND PERSONAL TRAINING DEVELOPMENT OF CADETS OF HIGHER MILITARY EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *This article covers the aspects of professional and personal training development of cadets of higher military educational institutions.*

Keywords: *higher military educational institutions, cadets, professional and personal training, professional ability, activity.*

By the formation of the necessary abilities, skills and abilities of a modern cadet, we mean the field of professional training of a cadet that teaches and educates. Knowledge, skills and abilities are formed throughout a person's life. There is a relationship between skills and competence, as the ability of cadets to perform their service obligations and duties depends on knowledge and experience. Therefore, the formation of skills to perform certain activities or actions in new conditions is carried out on the basis of existing knowledge and skills. As a result of the formation of professional skills, a personal change of the cadet takes place.

Abilities are understood as individual psychological properties that make a person capable of a certain activity, because the ease of acquiring knowledge and skills in a certain activity depends on abilities.

According to N.M. Platonova [2], professional abilities represent a set of stable individual-psychological qualities and properties of a person that determine the success of professional education or activity in a specific specialty.

Thus, the process of formation of professional knowledge, skills and abilities is a blind, active theoretical and practical activity of cadets, the success of which depends on abilities, stability of professional motivation and voluntary efforts.

It should be noted that personal development does not occur in any activity. For this to happen, the activity must be saturated with elements of creativity, arouse interest and emotional excitement in a person. It is an active subject of personal development.

In the process of activity, personal properties are connected with each other in a certain way according to the requirements of activity and form complex structures. The following are among such structures: temperament (a system of natural properties), orientation (a system of needs, interests, interests, ideals), abilities (a network of intellectual, volitional and emotional properties), character (a synthesis of attitudes and behavior patterns); these substructures "represent a high level of regulation of activity and behavior (how to behave) in accordance with the situation and the students of the labor system", as well as provide psychological readiness to perform professional activities.

The advantage of focusing (orienting) the process of training a military specialist on the individual is that it is within the framework of a single model that allows describing the characteristics of the level of expression and interrelationships of individual-psychological

qualities and properties in order to predict the professional development of all the indicated sub-structures of the student's personality. presentation is very important.

There is no doubt that the appropriate prediction of the professional development of the learner must be based on a clear understanding of the blind dimensional structure of the person. Naturally, this promotes the creation of a model of the learner that allows him to do the following:

- describe the personal characteristics of students in an appropriate (adequate) way;
- to determine stable psychological types of learners according to certain classification bases.

This makes it possible to develop psychological-edagogical recommendations on the organization of psychological support of the educational process, the implementation of an individual approach to teaching, the creative realization of students' opportunities, abilities and potential.

Using the qualities of learners for the purposes of this research, we will consider one of the systematization options created on the basis of a systematic approach in the theory of personality. In our opinion, the option of building on the basis of the information (information), which is called "rortret" of the cadet's personality and based on which it is possible to draw a conclusion about the cadet's potential opportunities in teaching, is a promising direction. Consistency and sequence of educational goals and main effects of this task, level of education are the starting conditions [3]. It includes the following: the formation of appropriate methods of actions affecting the educational process in students, their stock of knowledge and individual characteristics.

From the above-mentioned points, it follows that the development of the model of the learner's personality requires the research of the individual characteristics of the trainees. However, it should be noted that the personal characteristics of students that determine the success of educational activities are not theoretically distinguished in the practice of the educational process. This is conditioned by the insufficient development of the psychological and educational aspects of the problem of individual differences, and the difficulty of identifying (defining, determining) the individual characteristics of learners. Experts distinguish three aspects of the problem of individualization in teaching [4; 5]:

- individual differences as a fundamental characteristic of a person;
- influence of individual differences on learning content and teaching conditions;
- taking into account individual differences in the design of training in order to improve the training of each person.

As we mentioned above, training is the most important process of formation of professional knowledge and qualities of future military specialists, in which education is the most important way to accelerate their (specialists') intellectual development and enrich various types of knowledge. is considered one of the rsatkish. In this case, education is a broad concept, and the cadet is not determined by the ability to directly repeat a specific set of taught knowledge.

Education is a concept that includes in its structure the ability to use knowledge, skills and abilities in military-professional activities. It is the basis for further development and progress in any field of service activity. Therefore, it is the education that gives positive results and is a sufficient indication of the success of the educational process.

One of the tasks of our research is to study the relationship between education in science and the system of individual characteristics.

Education determines the existence of such a foundation for future studies. Therefore, it is appropriate to associate information about the success of education in the future with a set of

personal factors that determine (determine) a high degree, are independent of external conditions and differ in time stability. Learning ability is a combination of personal factors.

The ability to learn is one of the serious components of the mental development of a cadet, a graded (positive result) description. It is the main indication of the cadet's readiness to study, acquire knowledge, acquire skills and abilities in a goal-oriented manner under the conditions of a specific system of education. If intellectual development simultaneously describes the amount of acquired (assimilated) knowledge and ability, then the ability to learn and teach describes absolutely the second of the indicated components [5].

In the process of researching this problem, it was shown that the individual ability to learn is expressed at different levels in different learners.

In various studies, it is emphasized that all learners differ from each other in different levels of reading ability. Individual differences in the ability to read are widely manifested in mastering various subjects and educational activities [2; 3; 4; 5].

Students with a high level of reading ability are characterized by the speed of analyzing these relationships from a clearly focused point of view, abstracting and generalizing the serious features of the analyzed situations, which together lead to an effective and deeper knowledge of the surrounding reality. provides. Emphasizing that the difference between cadets with different educational abilities is manifested, first of all, in the amount of specific material that they need to master in order to draw independent conclusions or draw conclusions, and in the methods and methods of mental activity. pass is appropriate.

When determining the structure and content of the model of the student as a subject of the educational process, we need to take into account the need to obtain a certain level of the student's education, which depends on the elements (factors) included in this model.

The external factors of education determine the nature, size and content of real education from a blind point of view. Personal factors determine the level of assimilation of the offered knowledge, the growth of real education, the ability to apply knowledge in military-professional activities. In other words, external factors determine what, how and why the cadet should be taught, and personal factors determine (show) what the cadet actually learned.

External factors are important for the success of educational activities. In this case, some of them can help the educational process, while others, on the contrary, can slow it down. A conclusion can be drawn about the capabilities of this system in the intellectual field based on the character and results of its activity.

Different methods were used to determine the list of qualities that determine (determine) the success of the educational process of a person. The method of interviews with leading reedagogs and psychologists of the higher military educational institution served as the main method among them. As a result, a list of personal qualities was compiled, the content of some expressions was clarified, some elements of the list were enlarged or, on the contrary, specified, non-living elements were removed. Content analysis of psychological and editorial literature was used as an additional source of information in developing the list.

In the course of the work, the personal qualities that describe the potential of the student, which are necessary for successful educational activity, were determined. Each of these qualities represents the degree of formation of the cadet's psychological properties.

This process is the main one in the activity of the higher military educational institution, because the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities are formed in the cadets to effectively perform their educational and professional tasks.

Taking into account the features of training cadets and qualification requirements at the higher military educational institution, the necessary competencies of cadets were determined for the effective implementation of independent military-professional activity.

F.Umarov in his scientific research on the development of professional competencies of future officers based on a complex approach includes professional-specialized, socio-psychological, command (management) and military-special competencies in the professional competencies of cadets [1]. The author believes that all graduates should have them, regardless of the nature of professional activity. The researcher included professional-specialized, command (management) and military-special groups of competencies in science-related competencies.

As a result of the analysis of the scientific sources studied in the framework of our research and our observations, we studied the com-retentions of the cadets of higher military educational institutions, which is the main problem of our research, into general professional and industry-oriented com-retentions:

General professional qualifications:

1. Socio-psychological competences - competences that ensure the achievement of high results in the process of activities carried out in different social groups and life situations.
2. Management (command) qualifications - qualifications that give a graduate of a higher military educational institution the opportunity to effectively conduct organizational and management activities and evaluate the achieved results.

Industry-specific qualifications:

3. Vocational-specialized competences - competences that enable practical application of specialized knowledge and contribute to systematic cognitive activities aimed at mastering new knowledge.
4. Military-special qualifications - professional qualifications aimed at solving tasks in accordance with their functional goals.

The structure (content) of the process of developing the professional and personal training of cadets includes the following elements that form important professional qualities necessary for further professional activity of graduates (see Figure 1.6):

the element of subject-object professional relations (higher educational institution, faculty command; composition of professors and teachers; cadets);

element of goal setting (purpose and tasks of this process);

meaningful element (defined by qualification requirements for graduates, educational programs of subjects);

technological element (methods, methods, forms and means of teaching and developing cadets in training);

evaluative-resultative element (criteria, indicators and methodology for evaluating the development of professional and personal training of cadets of higher military educational institutions).

Thus, substantiating the structure and content of the learner's personality model based on the above made it possible to solve the task of objectively diagnosing the success of training cadets

at the Higher Military Educational Institution based on the development of the methodology for dividing the thyrological groups of learners.

The considered factors were selected as raremeters, which are the basis for determining the criterion of similarity between personal qualities. The positive aspect of this competition is that it is possible to draw conclusions about the intellectual level of cadets, the quality of the teaching process, and the conditions of daily work at a higher military educational institution, knowing the results of private (separate) performances.

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